

On the somatotopic mapping of acknowledgment haptic feedback of a sensorimotor interface

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Abstract—Supernumerary Robotic Limbs (SRL) represent a new class of robots whose aim is to augment the human body’s possibilities, for example extending its workspace. To control them the user must use a dedicated interface, which can both extract inputs from the human body and provide feedback about the robot’s status. Such a device is called a sensorimotor interface and the feedback subsystem is usually a wearable haptic device. The brain’s human somatotopic arrangement in the central nervous system lacks a location for artificially added limbs. In this extended abstract, we investigate if there is the best location for feedback coming from a robot not directly associated with a part of the wearer’s body. We have tested four different body locations - shoulder, wrist, hip, and ankle - for vibrotactile feedback coming from the simulated interaction with an extra robotic limb activated using an interface consisting of an accelerometer worn on the user’s shoulder. Results from the experiment involving 14 participants demonstrated that the ankle feedback position led to significantly worse performances when having input from the shoulder, whereas the other three locations led to comparable results.

Index Terms—Somatotopic mapping, Sensorimotor Interface, Wearable Haptics, Human-Robot Interface, Wearable Interface, Vibrotactile Feedback.

I. INTRODUCTION

Wearable robots are typically referred to as mechatronic systems built around human bodies, with joints and body segments that are equivalent to those of the wearer [1]. All exoskeletons created in the last few decades are perfectly suited to this definition. A new generation of wearable robots, however, has emerged in recent years that are intended to extend rather than enhance human body functions. These robots have been introduced as Supernumerary Robotic Limbs (SRL) [2] and are designed to be worn on the human body, but with their own kinematic structures that do not always resemble that of human limbs. In addition to the mechatronic difficulties in designing a lightweight, portable SRL, there are two other problems that need to be solved: how to control the motion of the SRL by a human, and how to provide the human

with significant task-execution feedback from the SRL, such as the forces exchanged with the environment.

The interplay of the interface and feedback is what makes these extra limbs effective [3]. Numerous solutions, including EMG interfaces [4] and the measurement of human body motion using devices like accelerometers [5], have been suggested for the interface’s input.

A fascinating new challenge for SRL is the haptic feedback. In actuality, there is no direct association between the wearable robot and the human body. They interact with the human by exchanging forces because they are grounded to the body. These forces can be understood by humans with proprioceptive information, such as the load carried by an additional arm [6]. There are, however, a variety of different signals that do not

Fig. 1. In the left part of the figure red dots represent the location selected to place the vibromotors. In the right part of the figure is shown the hardware setup mounted on a subject. It is shown by the arrows: the input device and the shoulder vibromotor (a); the output system, the Robotic Sixth Finger, and the wrist vibromotor (b); the vibromotor placed on the hip (c); the vibromotor placed on the ankle (d); the button to measure the reaction of the subject (e).

directly correspond to the human body, such as the strength of a gripper used as an end-effector for an SRL. Is it preferable to show this force on the body part where the robot is attached? Maybe another place would be a better location for displaying these signals.

In this extended abstract, we evaluated the best placement for a feedback signal from a robotic extra finger operated by a shoulder-mounted motion reading interface. The shoulder, where the interface is located, the wrist, where the extra finger is body grounded, the hip, and the ankle, which both feature bony prominences, were investigated as potential locations for the feedback. These positions are shown in Fig. 1. Following the activation of the finger motion through the interface, we timed how quickly subjects responded to a vibration burst that was randomly provided in one of the four locations as an acknowledgment. In the experiment, there were 14 participants. Only the ankle has a statistically significant worsening of the outcomes among the locations, as we were able to show.

II. THE EXPERIMENT

As a first step toward the study of somatotopic mapping for SRL, we design a simplified experiment involving an interface for extra finger control, the Robotic Sixth Finger [7] and four haptic interfaces located at shoulder, hip, wrist and ankle. The locations were chosen for the following reasons. The shoulder is the place where the input device is located and it is interesting to evaluate if a co-location of input and feedback device may be beneficial. The wrist was the location where the sixth finger was physically grounded on the subject body. The hip and the ankle were chosen for two main reasons: they represent a medium and a long distance from the input device and they have a bony prominence that may be exploited for better transmission of the vibrations.

The task consisted in moving up the shoulder as if we would like to start finger flexion. After the shoulder upward movement event recognition a random delay is introduced to avoid learning effect. The delay may range from 100 to 300 ms, 1 to 3 s or may be absent. Then, the system generates a vibration feedback, acknowledging the correct shoulder motion, in one of the four locations. As soon as the subject feels the vibration, he/she has to press a button to confirm the feedback perception. The performance metric used in this work is the measure of the voluntary reaction time after the haptic stimulus is sensed by the user. In other words, we evaluated if the perception of the vibration was faster in one of the locations. Moreover, we asked to participants to express their feedback location preference by means of a 7-point Likert scale to collect a qualitative preference.

We measured the reaction time, which is defined as the interval between the beginning of motor vibration and the voluntary push of the button.

Fourteen volunteers between the ages of 20 and 35 took part in the study. For a total of 280 reaction times per feedback site, 20 reaction time measurements from each subject were collected for each vibromotor. The experiment was repeated

with three delay conditions obtaining 3600 reaction time measurements.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The Shapiro-Wilk test revealed that the reaction time data distributions were normal. For each delay condition, a one-way ANOVA was performed. As demonstrated in Fig. 2, the one-way ANOVA did identify statistically significant differences between the feedback conditions.

It is worth noting that the shoulder positioning outperformed the ankle positioning ($p < 0.02$, $p < 0.0007$, $p < 0.0001$) in all conditions. Another statistically significant finding was that the performance of the ankle location was worse with respect to the other selected positions. Additionally, as shown in Fig. 3, a 7-point Likert scale questionnaire supported the finding that ankle location is the least effective. The purpose of this work is to take a preliminary step toward knowing the appropriate placement of haptic feedback from a robotic supernumerary limb that lacks a direct and evident somatotopic mapping. Our research was based on the hypothesis that the reaction time to a haptic stimulus is faster in the area of the body close to the activated muscle when that muscle is used to initiate the motion of the supernumerary limb, in this case the shoulder motion that initiates the flexion or the extension of the sixth finger. This study is underpinned by the physiology of muscles because when a muscle is contracting, it constantly sends proprioceptive kinaesthetic feedback via very fast conduction fibres to the cerebellum for movement correction and to the primary somatosensory cortex. Skin

Fig. 2. Results of the experiment under the three delay conditions: without a feedback foreperiod (top), with a variable delay in the range 100 to 300 ms (middle), or with a variable delay in the range 1000 to 3000 ms (bottom).

Fig. 3. Results of the 7-point scale Likert questionnaire completed by subjects after the experiment.

stretch brought on by muscular action also provides cutaneous feedback [8].

The hypothesis was not supported by our testing, and except from the ankle, no statistically significant advantages were found in the area being tested. The type of feedback is one explanation as to why this outcome occurred. It is likely that the above-mentioned neurological signalling, which can be thought of as a controller for movement correction, is not sufficiently elicited by a vibration burst, easily understood as a discrete event. Skin physiology would be a second explanation that may apply. Given that tactile innervation densities in the locations where feedback was given are essentially identical [9], it is even plausible that the user performs similarly in every part of the body unless the feedback is positioned very far away from the input, such as the ankle in relation to the shoulder.

A new experiment should be conducted to test the hypothesis that the reaction time to acknowledgement feedback is shortened when the feedback is located in the same body part of the input. The timing of the person clicking a button significantly increases the variability of the measurements, and more importantly, they do not match the speed of bio-potential signals. By utilising microneedle electrodes to investigate the muscular onset of the muscles responsible for button pressing [10], one hypothetical experiment would evaluate reaction time in a precise but far more invasive manner. A different, more practical method would be to assess the performances by making use of the continuous haptic feedback. Given that there are numerous circumstances in which a robot can perceive continuous time-varying data from the environment, this approach would be non-invasive and simple to deploy (e.g. feedback proportional to the sensed force of a robot). Participants who spontaneously provided feedback on the experimental design stated that the location of the haptic input

was irrelevant. The individuals expected feeling a vibration cue since they were focused on pressing the button to do the reaction task, and even though the haptic cue arrived at an unpredictable time, they were ready to react to it.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

We concluded that physically placing a haptic feedback channel on the ankle is not a reasonable option when designing a human-robot interface whose input is located on the shoulder. Since these body components are distanced from one another, the location of the ankle is inconvenient for a manufacturer. The ankle is not a useful solution from an application standpoint because two devices must be worn by the user to complete this bidirectional connection with the robot. By analysing reaction times to an acknowledgement, the data collected for this experiment did not demonstrate that any of the four locations where we placed the haptic feedback is more effective. However, our findings do not exclude the possibility that haptic feedback might be more beneficial if it is positioned in one body part rather than another. We did not find evidence to support our hypothesis, which theorised that the haptic feedback would be located close to the input. The hypothesis we formulated, which would locate the haptic feedback close to the input, was not rejected. Our intent for the future is to further explore this hypothesis by providing a continuous haptic feedback to the subject, *i.e.* a haptic stimulus proportional to some sensed task parameter. Such an implementation is non-invasive and maintains the applicative aspect of the research question.

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